

did not support pathovar growth up to 10 d incubation. *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* is generally less susceptible to antibiotics such as 0.001% amoxycillin, 0.001% ampicillin, or 0.005% neomycin than *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. None of the phenotypic features was correlated with the virulence of the strains. It was not possible to phenotypically differentiate the pathogenic races or groups of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*.

Brown blotch strains share many features with *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and pv. *oryzicola*. They are singly-occurring gram-negative rods; they metabolize glucose oxidatively; they are catalase positive, indole negative, urease negative, nitrate reductase negative; they produce acid from D-glucose, are strictly aerobic, and do not utilize L-asparagine as sole C and N source. However, there are some striking differences between BB and BLS pathogens (see table). Besides those features, the following tendencies for differentiation exist: brown blotch isolates

Differentiation between the bacteria causing BB, BLS, and brown blotch on rice, RUG-IRRI.

	BB (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>)	BLS (<i>X. campestris</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i>)	Brown blotch
Acetoin production	-	+	-
Oxidase	-	-	-
H ₂ S from peptone	+	+	-
Hydrolysis of TWEEN 60 and 80	+	+	-
Growth on L-alanine as sole C source	-	+	+
Growth on glycerol or sodium propionate as sole C source	-	-	+
Growth on 0.2% vitamin-free casamino acids	-	+	+
Growth on Kado and Heskett's selective medium	-	-	+
Resistance towards			
0.001% Cu(NO ₃) ₂	+	-	+
0.001% 8-hydroxyquinoline	-	-	+
0.001% ZnO	-	-	+

are gelatinase negative against 49% positives for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* and 100% for *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, do not hydrolyze arbutin (91% and 67% positives), and are erythromycin resistant (0% and 7%).

Furthermore, they grow luxuriantly on Döbereiner N-free medium. DNA:rRNA hybridizations and % G+C determination showed that brown blotch isolates definitely do not belong in *Xanthomonas*. □

Severe ufra outbreak in transplanted rice in Bangladesh

S. A. Miah and M. L. Rahman, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

The transplanted rice crop in the 5,000-ha Dhaka-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) irrigation project area, about 20 km southeast of Dhaka, was badly infested by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. Transplanted rice is continuously cropped in the project area except in some high elevation fields where mustard is grown in dry season. Symptoms

were white-splash pattern chlorosis, brown spots on leaves and culms at the growing points, and delayed panicle emergence.

Sporadic ufra attacks were first reported in early 1979. Disease incidence has gradually increased, with occasional severe outbreaks (see table). In Sep 1984 almost all fields were affected, with 5-100% infestation. Severity ranged from mild chlorosis to panicle nonemergence. Some plots were destroyed and farmers cut the plants for hay.

Most farmers used no ufra control, although a few used furadan at one-third the recommended dose of 33 kg/ha or 1.0 kg ai/ha. Fields previously planted to

mustard were least affected. About 7.5% of production (7,000-8,000 t) may be lost. Preliminary results of experiments with potted plants indicate that recommended doses of furadan, disulfoton, or fenamiphos applied to soil or as a foliar spray may cure infested plants. □

Estimated ufra severity and yield loss over several years in the DND project area, Bangladesh.

Year	Crop ^a	Infested fields (%)	Severity as % infested plants	Yield loss (%)
1978	T. aman	20-30	10-40	10
1981	Born	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	10-15	10-20	5
1982	Boro	10-15	10-20	5
	T. aman	20-25	10-40	10
1983	Boro	20-25	10-20	5
	T. aman	40-50	30-100	50
1984	Born	40-50	30-40	40
	T. aman	90-100	60-100	60-75

^a T. aman = transplanted aman.

Bacterial leaf streak (BLS) incidence in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh

V. D. Naidu, assistant plant pathologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Agricultural Research Station, Nelbre 524004, India

In late kharif 1983-84, a serious BLS outbreak, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*, occurred at Nellore for the first time. We surveyed farmers fields from Sep to Dec 1983 to assess disease severity.

The first BLS symptoms were observed the first week of Oct on 50- to 80-d-old, NLR9672, although all varieties developed typical symptoms. Varieties grown on smaller areas include NLR9674, NLR27999, and BCP.1. All the varieties